

THICK-WALLED WOUND COMPOSITE STRUCTURES.

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The paper presents a survey of works with allowance for high transverse compliance of various types of current composite materials, developed over the past years. It deals in detail with the cases of rejection of the elastic circular winding model, the effect of initial imperfections, the ways of evaluation and account of physical nonlinearity of the radial stress-strain relationship for thick-walled essentially anisotropic rings, submitted to uniform pressure, the account of the compressibility of a normal in case of bending test of bars with a circular axis and made from high-modulus materials and the efficiency of radial reinforcement of wound structures. It has been shown that the increased transverse compliance of a semi-finished product and end products, the peculiarities induced by the increased compliance and the ways of their elimination have proved to be among the major problems in the development of thick-walled wound structures.

Introduction

The fibrous composites based on a polymer matrix were initially mainly employed for the development of thin-walled structures. Experience and the problems arisen in the area have been reviewed in monographs [1-6]. As might be expected, the properties of composites in the plane of reinforcement were of supreme concern in case of thin-walled structures. The increase in thickness of wound structures from fibrous composites has directed interest toward strength and deformation characteristics of the material in the direction, perpendicular to the plane of layup of reinforcing fibers. Numerous investigations of plastics reinforced with glass-, boron-, carbon- and organic fibers (their survey is presented in [7-9]), have shown that high-modulus fiber reinforced materials exhibit increased compliance in the transverse direction due to the presence of a polymer matrix. In the development of thick-walled wound structures the allowance for the increased transverse compliance $\frac{1}{E_r}$ of a semi-finished product and end products becomes essential. The complexity of the problem lies in the fact that the degree of anisotropy of the material β undergoes variation in different stages of the winding process, the modulus in the fiber direction E_θ remaining practically constant; only E_r changes. Consequently, we have to deal with materials having different transverse properties, that is, a semi-finished product and the end product.

Transverse Compliance.

β^2 of a semi-finished product amounts to 400-2000, depending on the type of fibers and the reinforcement pattern; i.e. elastic moduli along and across the

length of fibers differ by 2 to 3 orders of magnitude. Increased compliance in the transverse direction is undoubtedly the cause of essential redistribution of initially given winding tension throughout the thickness of the product and the source of development of highly dangerous initial stresses. The fact necessitated the optimization of force and temperature regimes for winding, curing and cooling and the search for new technological procedures. Winding tension can be controlled only in the stage of production of a semi-finished product. The method of solving such problems is treated in works [10-12]. The realization of optimum programs enables us to develop structures with a given epure of initial radial stresses Fig. 1 .

The technological problems of winding mechanics have been thoroughly investigated in works [13-15]. The analytical description of winding mechanics is based on an elastic circular model [16]; the problems pertaining to helical winding of loops and inelastic properties of the polymer matrix in compression of a semi finished product constitute an exception. Problems of the effect of fiber curvature on the properties of wound products from high-modulus fiber reinforced composites and the choice of optimum winding tension also required more elaborated approach.

Winding materials, especially those reinforced with carbon and organic fibers, are distinguished by high transverse compliance not only in the production stage but also in the end product. For structures from carbon and organic plastics the relationship is as follows $\beta^2 = \frac{E_\theta}{E_r} \leq 50$ [17-19]. The necessity of revision of the scope of applicability of the hypothesis about incompressibility of a normal in flexure problems has arisen. This refers to the determination of deflections

as well as transverse tensile stresses, which are especially dangerous for materials with low resistance to lateral tearing. Imparting the material with infinite transverse rigidity has led to erroneous estimation of load carrying capacity of structures, the reasons of failure and processing of the results of mechanical testing, especially on circular samples. The necessity of establishing the criterion of thick-wallness has arisen, i.e. of such a thickness-to-diameter ratio, at which for a given anisotropy we may restrict our attention to the first term of expansion of the exact solution into a power series through the thickness. Methods of study of the properties of wound materials and technics of processing the measured results are the corollaries of the problem. Attempts of the generalization of the experience obtained in the testing of composites on circular samples were made in work [20].

The rise in thickness of wound structures and in strength of the reinforcing fibers has directed attention not only toward the degree of anisotropy β_* and β but also to the type of the relationship $\sigma_r - \epsilon_r$. When we have to deal with structures operating under uniform pressure of thousands of atmospheres the radial stresses σ_r^* amount to such a degree that our interest can no longer be confined to the initial zone of the curve $\sigma_r - \epsilon_r$ and its form neglected. A detailed study of stress-strain relationship up to the very failure becomes necessary, which is associated with serious technical difficulties. Measurements indicated essential nonlinearity of the relationship $\sigma_r - \epsilon_r$ in compression perpendicular to the reinforcing fibers [21]. The fact required formulation and solution of the problems of stress-strain state of thick-wall-

ed rings, taking into account physical nonlinearity of the material. The necessity of regarding the nonlinear properties in the radial direction is also to be faced in analyzing the performance of three-ply wound structures with a compliant filler, for example, foamed plastic. The type of the relationship $\sigma_r - \epsilon_r$ in the problems affects the stress transfer from the composite to the external (or internal) pressure-free layer. The problem gets more complicated when we pass over to special types of winding and the use of organic fibers. In the cases the necessity of considering nonlinearity not only in the radial but also in the circumferential direction may arise [22] .

Stiffening of the material in the transverse direction is performed by means of radial reinforcement. The spherical structures for deep submergence made by the technique are well-known [23] .The technological difficulties involved in the winding of a pattern with radial filaments become evident. Consequently, a thorough tentative analysis and experimental verification of the efficiency of radial layup of armature and the assessment of the range of relative thicknesses over which radial reinforcement is effective should be performed on models.

The problem of initial stresses in wound structures and results obtained in the area are thoroughly treated in work [13]; an exhaustive bibliography up to 1972 is also enclosed. In the following years mainly the acquisition of experimental data has been realized, thereby the inbreak into the region of large relative thicknesses up to $\frac{h}{R_i} \leq 0,5$ (h is the thickness, R_i is the inner radius) and pressures up to several thousand atmospheres was crowned with success ([24, 25] et al.). The range of problems investi-

gated has been extended, a series of new technological procedures has been suggested and studied: winding with heating, winding under extra pressure, winding through a narrow hole [26], winding with subsequent layer-by-layer cure (Fig. 2) [27]. Let us consider the new problems pertaining to the cases of rejection the circular winding model, the ways of study and consideration of physical nonlinearity of the relationship $\sigma_r - \epsilon_r$ for thick-walled rings, operating under uniform pressure, and the compressibility of a normal under loading with concentrated forces and the efficiency of radial reinforcement.

The survey in accordance with the requirements of the Conference Committee has been based on works concerning the scope of interests of the author and should not be considered exhaustive.

Rejection of the Circular Model.

In the elastic circular model the helical winding is substituted by concentric circular one. *)

) Naturally, the linearization of the relationship $\sigma_r^ - \epsilon_r^*$ for a semi-finished product itself presents a rough approximation. Yet, as a rule, the contact pressure, determining the level of σ_r^* , is very low. At the level of compressive radial stresses the linearization is quite allowable, especially for winding procedure, when filtration of the binder is permitted only on end surfaces. Calculations [30] have revealed that the resulting error in many cases of practical interest does not exceed 10 %.

The fact excludes the peculiarities, associated with discontinuity of reinforcement on the inner and outer surfaces and the deviation from ideal axisymmetry, from the area under consideration. The first peculiarity is manifested in terms of a specific type of failure - unwinding [5, 15, 28] ; a review of works, dealing with the kind of failure, has been given in the reference [32], The second peculiarity leads to the development of tangential stresses $\tau_{r\theta}$, existing through the entire thickness of a ring:

$$\tau_{r\theta} = \left[(\rho \rho_0^{\beta+1} - q)(\beta+1) \left(\frac{r}{R_0} \right)^{\beta-1} + (\rho - q \rho_0^{\beta-1}) \rho_0^{\beta+1} \left(\frac{R_0}{r} \right)^{\beta+2} \right] \quad (I)$$

Here q and ρ are external and internal pressures, respectively; ρ_0 is the ratio between the inner R_i and outer R_0 radii of a ring; $\beta = \sqrt{\frac{E_g}{E_r}}$; c is the thickness of the elementary layer, consisting of armature and a polymer interlayer.

When compliance of the matrix is very high (that of a semi-finished product, at elevated temperatures etc.), the low tangential stresses may cause essential shear strains [33] .As a consequence of the shear strain the loops are shifted as regards one another. At constant pressure ρ_0 the phenomenon is manifested in extra radial displacements Δr_i ; in the case of description the matrix properties through the equation of " a typical body" the maximum radial displacements are following:

$$\max \Delta r = \frac{\rho_0 c H}{4\pi^2 R_i G \ln R_0 / R_i} \quad (2)$$

Here G is the total rigidity of the elements of the model of " a typical body". For systems with guaranteed tensioning the slippage of loops leads to the

fall in the given winding tension.

Another case of rejection of the circular model is the possible curvatures of the reinforcing layers. In an analytical description of the effect of curvatures on the properties of composites, reinforced with anisotropic fibers, it was necessary to consider not only the low shear strength as for GFRP, but also the ratio of elastic moduli along and across the length of fibers. In case of weak regular sinusoidal curvatures, without neglect of the value of f^2 compared to a unity, the expression of elastic modulus in the fiber direction E_{θ}^* takes the following form:

$$E_{\theta}^* = E_{\theta} \left\{ \frac{2+f^2}{2(1+f^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{E_{\theta}}{G_{r\theta}} \frac{f^2}{2(1+f^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{E_{\theta}}{E_r} \left[1 - \frac{2+3f^2}{2(1+f^2)^{3/2}} \right] \right\}^{-1} \quad (2a)$$

where E_{θ} is the modulus of elasticity of the material in tension along the straightened fibers; $G_{r\theta}$ is interlaminar shear modulus; f is a parameter, characterizing the fiber curvature. The effect of $\frac{E_{\theta}}{E_r}$ is illustrated in Fig. 3; for relatively high values of curvatures the effect of the term, containing $\frac{E_{\theta}}{E_r}$ as a multiplier, becomes essential. The experimental verification of the relationship (2a) on CFRP rings with a given value of curvature of fibers indicated sufficient accuracy of the approach described [18].

Consideration of Physical Nonlinearity.

Let us refer to the account of physical nonlinearity. The simplest example is the design of a thick-walled ring, operating under uniform pressure. In the first approximation nonlinearity of the relation $\sigma_r - \epsilon_r$ was accounted for in terms of the simplest model, representing a composite ring with a movable boundary between two elastic rings; the boundary between zones

runs along the radius r_0 , along which radial stresses are equal to σ_r^* . The relationship $\sigma_r - \epsilon_r$ is approximated by two straight lines; the coordinate of crossover point is σ_r^* . It is reached at the pressure equal to p^* . Up to p_i (or p_o) = p^* the ring is uniform as stresses exhibit a linear dependence on pressure; at $p_i > p^*$ the relationship becomes nonlinear. An area with increased compliance in the radial direction and elastic modulus $E_r^{(2)}$ appears in the ring. The radius of the boundary r_0 depends upon the pressure. The way of description of the deformation properties in the ring area, where $\sigma_r > \sigma_r^*$, is governed by the choice of the model.

Hoop stresses on the inner radius $\sigma_{\theta Ri}^{(2)}$, along which compressive pressure p_i was applied, may be represented in terms of a piecewise linear model according to the formula [32] :

$$\sigma_{\theta Ri}^{(2)} = \frac{p^*}{2} \left[\left(\beta_1 \frac{n^{2\beta_1} + \beta_o^{2\beta_1}}{n^{2\beta_1} - \beta_o^{2\beta_1}} - \beta_2 \right) n^{\beta_2 - 1} + \left(\beta_1 \frac{n^{2\beta_1} + \beta_o^{2\beta_1}}{n^{2\beta_1} - \beta_o^{2\beta_1}} + \beta_2 \right) n^{-(\beta_2 + 1)} \right] \quad (3)$$

$n = R_i / r_o$; $\beta_o = R_i / R_o$ R_i is inner, R_o is outer radius;
 $\beta_1 = \sqrt{E_{\theta}^{(1)} / E_r^{(1)}}$; $\beta_2 = \sqrt{E_{\theta}^{(2)} / E_r^{(2)}}$ the notations of elastic constants are evident. The expression for the computation of $\sigma_{\theta R_o}^{(2)}$ under external pressure has an analogous form; by setting n in the range of $\beta_o < n \leq 1$, the ratio between pressure and stresses, existing throughout the cross sections of a ring, may be found. Analysis of the obtained relationship has shown that nonlinearity of the relation $\sigma_r - \epsilon_r$ leads to a sharp rise in hoop stresses σ_{θ} on the surface under internal or external pressure (Table I), but the account of nonlinearity of $\sigma_r - \epsilon_r$ for unidirectional composites results in an essential change in $\max \sigma_{\theta}$, even for relatively thin rings.

A qualitative effect of nonlinearity on the re-distribution of stresses through the thickness of the ring is illustrated by an experimentally detected delay of deformations on the load-free surface (Fig.4); deformations were measured by means of electromechanical strain gages up to the failure of samples. The difficulties of quantitative evaluation of the resulting maximum stresses from the experimental data lie in the fact that the unloading of the free surface is considerably weaker than the "overloading" of inner loops. This is clearly seen from Table I, drawn for materials with greatly differing nonlinearity.

Table I

Ratio of stresses $\frac{\sigma_{\theta}}{\sigma_{\theta}^*}$ for rings of various thicknesses.

Internal pressure kg /cm ²	Surface	Materials			
		A - 20		A - 100	
		Relative thickness		Relative thickness	
		0,883	0,714	0,883	0,714
1000	Loaded under pressure	1,01	1,06	1,39	2,26
	Pressure-free	1,00	0,99	0,86	0,72
2500	Loaded under pressure	1,05	1,31	2,63	6,23
	Pressure-free	0,99	0,93	0,61	0,30

A - 20: material with weak nonlinearity; A - 100: material with high nonlinearity. σ_{θ} is calculated in terms of the suggested models; σ_{θ}^* is calculated according to elastic approach.

More accurate evaluation of hoop stresses, being dangerous for load carrying capacity of structures, required a reasonable elaboration of the design model. G.G. Portnov has treated two improved variants of the composite circular model (Fig. 5), devoid of the main drawback of the former model, associated with discontinuity in deformations on the boundary surface. In the first case it was assumed that at $\sigma_r \geq \sigma_r^*$

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{\sigma_r}{E_r^{(2)}} - \sigma_r^* \left(\frac{1}{E_r^{(2)}} - \frac{1}{E_r^{(1)}} \right) \quad (4)$$

In the second case the radial modulus of elasticity of one of the rings was assumed to undergo variation according to the exponential law

$$E_r^{(2)} = E_r^{(1)} \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right)^w \quad (5)$$

or $E_r^{(2)} = E_r^{(1)} \left(\frac{r_0}{r} \right)^w$ depending on the fact, whether the area was located inside or outside of r_0 , in which $\sigma_r > \sigma_r^*$. The exponent w has been chosen in such a way that the deformation of the loaded surface was approaching the relationship $\sigma_r - \varepsilon_r$.

More exact evaluation of the state of stress has been obtained by Yu. N. Rabotnov's approach [33] from the standpoint of nonlinear theory of elasticity for anisotropic body, assuming that the stress-strain relationship on uniaxial loading along the principal axes of anisotropy is characterized by power functions of the type:

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{\sigma_i}{E_i} + f\left(\frac{\sigma_i}{E_i}\right) \quad (6)$$

The relationship (6) has been employed for the experimental evaluation of the necessary constants; the

methodology of evaluation of constants is thoroughly dealt with in [34]. For the given problem, when the material along the tangential coordinate follows Hooke's law, only three constants should be experimentally determined. The numerical solution of the problem has been performed on a digital computer by the technique of iteration. Naturally, the latter approach is more logical but at the same time more time consuming. A considerably simpler and more visual approach, based on the use of relationship (4), may be employed with sufficient accuracy.

The necessity of considering the physical non-linearity of the material arises also for three-ply structures with a compliant filler, operating under uniform pressure. Nonlinear behavior of the filler in compression results in the overloading of the load carrying layer on the side of the applied pressure. Characteristic results, obtained in the testing of three-ply rings, having the internal diameter of 360 mm, are presented in Fig. 6 [35]. The relationship $\sigma_r - \epsilon_r$ for the filler was approximated by means of the expression:

$$\epsilon_r = \frac{1}{B} \ln \left(\frac{\pi_r^-}{\pi_r^- - \sigma_r} \right) \quad (7)$$

B is a material constant; π_r^- is compressive strength of foamed plastic. The calculated data are enclosed in the same figure. The sign - stands for tension; + for compression.

Compressibility of a Normal.

Compressibility of a normal was investigated on an anisotropic ring, loaded in compression by concentrated forces [36]. The basic attention was directed toward radial displacements and the determina-

tion of the value of tensile stress σ_r^+ . In contrast to former approaches, when the boundary pressure, operating along a certain small arc of the circumference (in the case the problem of proper choice of the zone length always remains open), was expanded into Fourier series, the latter approach employs the technique of expansion into Fourier series of internal integral circumferential and radial forces through ring sections. In this case the solution independent of the contact area is obtained.

It was shown in the case of loading with two diametrically applied forces that deflections taking into account the radial deformations may undergo an essential change only for rings with $\rho_0 = \frac{R_i}{R_o} \leq 0,8$, whereas the error becomes noticeable only for thick-walled rings with a high degree of anisotropy (Fig.7). For the correct calculation of deflections of the ring loaded in compression with diametrically applied forces the following refined formula has been obtained:

$$W = \frac{P}{\pi b E_\theta} \left[\frac{1}{\ln \rho_0} + \frac{8}{(\ln \rho_0)^3} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha_m^3 \cos 2m\theta}{(\alpha_m - \tanh \alpha_m)(4m^2 - 1)} \right] \quad (8)$$

in which after approximation ^{$\ln \rho_0$} the first term of expansion into a power series in the vicinity of the mean radius coincides with the familiar formula from the strength theory of materials. Here b is width of a ring

$$\alpha_m = \frac{1 + 4m^2 \left(\frac{E_\theta}{G_{re}} - 2 \nu_{re} \right)}{2} \ln \rho_0$$

The radial stresses near the points of application of concentrated compressive forces may change the sign and reach the values, comparable to the ultimate strength of the material in tension, perpendicular to the fibers. For CFRP rings ($\beta^2 = \frac{E_\theta}{E_r} = 30+50$; $\alpha^2 = \frac{E_\theta}{G_{re}} =$

= 150+200) the calculation of σ_r in terms of the angular and radial coordinates has been performed. An approximate formula for the case of anisotropy may be presented in the following form:

$$\sigma_r = \frac{P}{\pi b R_0} (\sigma_{r_0} + \sigma_{r_\Sigma}) \quad (9)$$

where $\sigma_{r_0} = \frac{\beta_0^{2\beta} \beta^{-\beta-1} - \beta^{\beta-1}}{1 - 2\beta_0^{2\beta}}$ characterizes the axisymmetrical part of expansion, complying with the problem of Lamé, but

$$\sigma_{r_\Sigma} = 2 \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{\left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right)^{\lambda_{1m}-2} (\lambda_{3m}-\lambda_{2m})(1-\lambda_{4m}) - \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right)^{\lambda_{2m}-2} (\lambda_{3m}-\lambda_{1m})(1-\lambda_{4m})(\lambda_{2m}-4m^2)}{(\lambda_{3m}-\lambda_{1m})(\lambda_{4m}-\lambda_{2m})\rho_0^{\lambda_{1m}} - (\lambda_{1m}-\lambda_{4m})(\lambda_{3m}-\lambda_{2m})\rho_0^{\lambda_{2m}}} \right] \cos 2m\theta \quad (10)$$

characterizes the deviation of radial stresses, caused by nonaxisymmetrical loading. Here $\beta = \frac{r}{R_0}$ is the variable relative radius, λ_{im} are roots of the inherent equation of plane problem for cylindrically orthotropic ring, loaded in compression with two concentrated forces. The remaining notations are evident. The expression (10) is approximate for the case $|\lambda_{3,4}| > |\lambda_{1,2}|$ and is fulfilled at a high degree of anisotropy α^2 and β^2 . It was established that positive radial stresses develop at a short distance from the line of action of concentrated forces. The anisotropy of material properties causes an essential change in the value of radial stresses with the increase in the ring thickness. The range of thicknesses and anisotropy has been established over which the account of the compressibility of a normal becomes necessary.

Consideration of σ_r is of significance in analyzing the test results for curved bars, loaded with concentrated forces. This may be readily seen from the approximated formula $\max \sigma_r = \frac{3}{2} \frac{M}{FR}$ [37]; M is bending moment, R is a radius of curvature, F is

the area of cross section. The effect of radial stresses on the type of failure of segments under three-point loading (the method has been standardized in the U.S.A. for the evaluation of interlaminar shear strength $\Pi_{r\theta}$) depends on the sign of beam flexure and the ratio of $\frac{\Pi_r^+}{\Pi_{r\theta}}$ and $\frac{l}{2R}$; where l is the distance between support points. For a positive curvature (convex), when $\frac{\Pi_r^+}{\Pi_{r\theta}}$ is near to $\frac{l}{2R}$ stress σ_r may be the cause of failure. The experiments performed on CFR plastics have confirmed the conclusion, drawn in [17] .

Radial Reinforcement.

The foregoing discussion has led to the idea of radial reinforcement. The preliminary calculations [38] , based on the hypothesis about the lack of interaction between stresses and strength of rings, and the experiments performed on model samples, prepared according to two different methods, have shown that pure radial reinforcement in the range of $1 < \frac{R_o}{R_i} \leq 2$ is inappropriate. At the same time radial reinforcement with some part of fibers may result in an essential increase in the load carrying capacity of rings. The optimum radial fiber content n_{opt} corresponding to the highest bursting pressure p_{opt} is equal to maximum, according to n , from the minimum value of the ratio between hoop strength and $\sigma_{\theta max}$ or compressive strength in the radial direction

$$p_{opt} = \max n \left[\min \left(\frac{\Pi_{\theta}^{(+)}}{\sigma_{\theta max}}, \text{ or } \Pi_r^- \right) \right]$$

The necessity of radial reinforcement for unidirectional GFRP and CFRP appears already in the range of $1, 1 < \frac{R_o}{R_i} < 1, 2$. The necessary radial fiber content in-

creases with the increase in relative thickness, though never exceeds 30 % in cases of practical interest. The load carrying capacity of stiffened rings increases faster than the necessary radial fiber content. Besides, the obtained increase in the load carrying capacity is rather essential.

Conclusions.

The above said allows us to conclude that increased compliance in the radial direction of composite winding materials and finished products, the peculiarities induced by it and the ways of their elimination form one of the basic problems in the development of thick-walled wound structures, the thorough investigation of which has only reached its initial stage.

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I. Initial stresses in GFRP rings, wound according to programs shown in the center of the figure

G_r^0 are radial stresses
 G_θ^0 are hoop stresses

2. Initial stresses in rings, wound with subsequent layer-by-layer cure according to programs 1-5.

3. Error, caused by disregard of transverse compliance in the evaluation of the effect of curvatures

- | | |
|----------|--|
| 1 - GFRP | $E_\theta / G_{r\theta} = 10, E_\theta / E_r = 5$ |
| 2 - CFRP | $E_\theta / G_{r\theta} = 30, E_\theta / E_r = 50$ |

4. Delay of circumferential deformations on the load-free surface

1 - B (100); 2 - A (100); 3 - A (20);
 4 - B (20). A - a rigid binder, B - a plastic binder; testing temperature in $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in brackets.
 $\xi_{\theta y}^{+(-)}$ is calculated according to elastic model.

5. Piece-wise linear and power approximation of deformation properties.

6. Rise in stresses in the internal carrying layer and reduction in the strains of a free carrying layer due to nonlinear properties of a filler.

ξ_{θ}^* , σ_{θ}^* are strains and stresses in case of linear deformation of a filler; ξ_{θ} , σ_{θ} the same in case of nonlinear deformation. The values of ξ_{θ} are obtained experimentally, ξ_{θ}^* , σ_{θ} are obtained according to the suggested model.

1 - ring with a filler B ($\Pi_{\bar{r}} = 27 \text{ kgf/cm}^2$, $B = 50$);
 2 - ring with a filler A ($\Pi_{\bar{r}} = 44 \text{ kgf/cm}^2$, $B = 38$).

7. Effect of compressibility of a normal on ring deflection under acting force.

W is complete deflection, W_c is deflection, calculated taking into account shear strains.